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CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN RURAL INDIA

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Abstract

A woman plays very significant role in the economic development of India. Women are participated in business activities at all stages, making important assistance to economic growth. Now-a-days, Indian women are more and more active in parts of the economy that were earlier considered male domain. Particularly in Rural areas women are constrained by the gender value, stereotypes and norms in the environment in which they work. Be their reproductive roles they tend to be accountable for business as well as for most of the unpaid work in the household (domestic responsibilities such as cooking the food, caring for children, cleaning and caring of other household members). Women's have fever time to devote to their work and they are less movable. They also face cultural and social barriers, because the overall view of society is that a woman's main duty is to be a mother and good housewife. Women are also often perceived as passive, weak, and irrational. Women entrepreneurship is considered as a key factor for Women Empowerment more than ever in Rural areas and hence promotion of Women entrepreneurs is paying attention highly by the Government. So there is a need of continuous attempt to encourage, inspire, cooperate and motivate Women entrepreneurs. Indian Government is also conducting special EDPs for women to encourage them to join industry. Some institutional arrangements at the centre as well as at state level are made like State Financial Corporations, District Industry Centre, Nationalized banks and other voluntary agencies like FICCI's FLO, NAYE (National alliance of young entrepreneurs) to promote women entrepreneurship. The present paper provides a brief idea about the importance to women entrepreneurship and opportunities and challenges faced by the women entrepreneurs in rural India.

Key words: Entrepreneurs, EDP, Empowerment

I. Introduction

The words of Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru “*When women move forward, the family moves, the village moves and the nation moves*” is the central theme in the socio-economic paradigm of the country as it is fact that only when women are in the main stream of progress can any economic and social development be meaningful. In the present global era, there is rapidly growth in the economy. In this progress woman’s participation having greater importance. These women entrepreneurs have usually gain latent from the Self Help Groups. In fact these Self Help Groups are making women as economically independent if not a sound one. They are emancipating their voice in all the phase of economy. A woman accepts challenging role to meet her personal requirements and become economically independent. A woman faces several problems to reach her domestic needs. At last, a women entrepreneur becomes independent after facing challenges. By identifying herself a triumphant entrepreneur, she shine in two faces of her life i.e. family and society. There has been a serious discussion taking place about gender bias. Apart from this gender inequality there are some unseen barriers to rural women’s entrepreneurship. The present paper throws light on the concept of opportunities and challenges of rural women entrepreneurs and reasons for slow growth of women entrepreneurs in rural India.

2. Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship refers to the act of starting up a new business or refreshing an existing business so as to take benefits from new opportunities. Thus, entrepreneurs outline the economy by creating new jobs new assets and by inventing new services and products. However, a deep study reveals that it is not about having the greatest ideas, making money, understanding the best sales pitch,

3. Women entrepreneurship

A woman entrepreneur is a mature who own and runs an enterprise, specially a commercial one, often at personal economic risk. The ILO defined the women’s enterprise as a small unit where one or more than one women entrepreneurs have not less than fifty per cent financial holdings.

The theory of women entrepreneurship is becoming a global phenomenon playing a very important role in the business society. In India, women have made a relatively late entry into business scenario mainly due to the conventional socio-cultural environment.

4. Objectives of the study:

1. To examine the problems faced by women entrepreneurs in rural India.
2. To look at the opportunities for rural women entrepreneurs.

5. Research Methodology

The study focus on wide-ranging study of Secondary data collected from various books, National & International Journals, Census Surveys, published reports of RBI, SSI Reports, NABARD, newspapers, publications from various websites which focused on several aspects of Women Entrepreneurship.

6. Major Challenges for Women Entrepreneurs in Rural Areas

The main challenges that women face in business are learning and work background, Balancing their time share between family and work, problems of introduce start-up capital, problem in borrowing fund, existence of small scale companies, problems of receiving raw-materials access to export market without mediators, as well as an overall psychological barricade on the part of banks, suppliers, and clients alike, are a some of these challenges. In addition to this some of the challenges faced by women in rural areas are as follows:

i) Absence of coordination between Career and Family Obligations

The majority of the women are very staid about family obligations but they do not regularly focus on career obligations. Indian women dedicate their lives to take care of their family members but they are not worried with their self-development. Many women have outstanding entrepreneurial abilities but they are not using their abilities to generate extra income sources for their families, which would go hand in hand with boosting their independence. Sometimes they are not even conscious of the concept of independence. Furthermore the business success depends on the support the family members in the business process and management.

ii) Low Degree of Financial Liberty

In Indian families, the degree of financial liberty for women is very low, particularly in rural families and lower educated families. In these families women can't take any commercial decision without the reflection of the family members as well as allowing for social ethics and background. Due to the financial need, a woman can't start any business or any economic activity to become self-governing. Therefore, this has become a vicious circle of dependency for women in rural India.

iii) Paradox of Finance & Entrepreneurial Skill

There is paradox of “have and haven't” skills of entrepreneurship in rural women belong to financially rich and poor families. Women belonging to financially rich families have the capital support but they may not have good entrepreneurial capability, therefore need of outsourcing the activities. At the opposite side of society, many women from financially poor families have steady entrepreneurial skills, but they have not any financial support from their families. We therefore believe that the problems of women entrepreneurship are hanging in the catch of this paradox.

iv) No Awareness about Capacities

An increasing level of education should create alertness about an individual's capacities. But, unfortunately, our educational system has not succeeded in creating attentiveness about woman's capacities and their unseen powers to hold economic activities. India faces an increase in the education level of women and an increased social alertness of the role women play in society, but this is not a broadly acceptable fact because it applies only in urban India and not in rural India. Urban atmosphere is good to identifying and creating attentiveness regarding women's self-capabilities. but in the rural area this type of attitude has not developed yet.

v) Lack of Professional Education

The educational level and professional skills also manipulate women participation in the field of enterprise. We are given that education to the women but not provide professional education. If we look in the professional business schools we find that there is a very a small number of female students. If we evaluate rural - urban ratio of enrolled female in professional education we recognize that there are very few rural female students enrolled in professional education.

Even guardian are not willing to send their daughters for undergoing professional education. Sometimes it happens, however, that many women taking the training by attending the entrepreneurial development program do not have an entrepreneurial bent of mind.

vi) Mobility Constraints

Mobility is one of the important problems in women commercial development. They are not willing to leave their place for business activities and wish staying only in their residential areas. These behavior are important as entrepreneurs be likely to start their businesses in their current local area and are thus unduly found in their region of birth.

vii) Lack of commercial aptitude

Lack of commercial aptitude is a major concern for rural women entrepreneurs. They have no entrepreneurial bent of brain. Sometimes even after participating several training program on entrepreneurship, women entrepreneurs fail to surge over the risks and troubles that may come up in a commercial working.

viii) Social Barriers

The conventions and customs established in Indian societies regarding women sometimes stand as an barrier before them to grow and prosper. Castes and religions dominate with one another and hinder women entrepreneurs too. In rural areas, they face more social obstacles as they are seen with doubtful eyes.

7. Opportunities:

i) Steps Taken By Government To get better Position of Women Entrepreneurs

Keeping in view the input of small business to employment generation, fair regional development of the country, and encouragement of exports, the Government of India's policy push on establishing, developing and promoting the small business sector, mainly the rural industries, village and cottage industries in backward areas. Governments at all level including

central and state have been aggressively participating in promoting self-employment opportunities in rural areas by providing support regarding infrastructure, raw materials, finance, training, technology and marketing. Some of the support measures and programs meant for the promotion of small and rural industries are discussed below:

ii) NATIONAL BANK FOR AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT (NABARD)

NABARD was set up in 1982 to support integrated rural development. Since then, NABARD has been adopting a multi-purpose, multi-pronged strategy for the encouragement of rural business enterprises in the country. Apart from agriculture, it supports cottage, small industries, village industries and rural artisans using non credit and credit approaches. NABARD offers consultancy and counseling services and organizes training and development programs for rural entrepreneurs.

iii) THE RURAL SMALL BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT CENTRE (RSBDC)

It is the first of this type set up by the world association for small and medium enterprises and is sponsored by NABARD. RSBDC works for the advantage of socially and economically disadvantaged groups and individuals. RSBDC aims at providing technical and management assistance to current and potential micro and small entrepreneurs in rural areas. Since its setting up, RSBDC has organized several programs on rural entrepreneurship, mobile clinics, skill up gradation workshops, and trainers training programs, awareness and counseling camps in various villages of Noida, Ghaziabad and Greater Noida.

iv) NATIONAL SMALL INDUSTRIES CORPORATION (NSIC)

This was set up in 1955 with a view to promote and foster the growth of small business units in the country. This focuses on the commercial aspects of these functions.

- a) Supply home-grown and imported machines on easy hire-purchase terms.
- b) obtain and supply home-grown and imported raw materials.
- c) Export the products of small business units and develop export-worthiness.
- d) Advisory and mentoring services.
- e) Creating awareness on technological up gradation.
- f) Developing software technology parks and technology transfer centres.

v) SMALL INDUSTRIES DEVELOPMENT BANK OF INDIA (SIDBI):-

SIDBI has been set up as an apex bank to make available direct/indirect financial help under different schemes, to meet credit requirements of small business organisations. SIDBI coordinates the functions of other institutions in related activities; suggest procedures considered necessary for improving the yield of small enterprises in the informal sector; create more employment opportunities on a sustainable basis, mainly in the rural areas and improve the competitiveness of the sector in the rising global environment.

vi) RURAL AND WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT (RWED):-

The Rural and Women Entrepreneurship Development program aims at promoting a conducive business environment and at building institutional and human capacities that will encourage and support the entrepreneurial initiatives of rural people and women.

RWE provides the following services:

- i) Creating a business environment that encourages initiatives of rural and women entrepreneurs.
- ii) Enhancing the human and institutional capacities required to foster entrepreneurial dynamism and enhance productivity.
- iii) Providing training manuals for women entrepreneurs and training them.
- iv) Rendering any other advisory services.

vii) WORLD ASSOCIATION FOR SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (WASME):-

It is the only International Nongovernmental Organization of micro, small and medium enterprises based in India, which set up an International Committee for Rural Industrialization. Its aim is to develop an action plan model for sustained growth of rural enterprises. Apart from these, there are several schemes to promote the non-farm sector, mostly initiated by the Government of India. For instance, there are schemes for entrepreneurship through subsidized loans like Integrated Rural Development Program (IRDP), Prime Minister Rojgar Yojana (PMRY), schemes to provide skills like Training of Rural Youth for Self Employment (TRYSEM), and schemes to strengthen the gender component like Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA).

.viii) THE DISTRICT INDUSTRIES CENTERS (DICS):-

The District Industries Centers Program was launched on May 1, 1978, with a view to provided that an integrated administrative structure at the district level, which would focus at the problems of industrialization in the district, in a combined manner. In other words, District Industries Centers is the institution at the district level and provides all the support and services facilities to the entrepreneurs for starting small and village industries.

Conclusion

Women are significant human resources of the country and every state should try to make use of them as mediators of economic development and growth. Encouragement for women entrepreneurship is one of the ways for that. But unfortunately it is seen that the traditional mind set of the society and negligence of the state and respective authorities are important obstacles in the women entrepreneurship development in India. Apart from the responsibility of the state and society, absence of a definite agenda of life, absence of balance between career and family obligations of women, poor level of financial freedom for women, lack of direct ownership of the assets to women, inconsistency of entrepreneurial skill & finance in economically rich and poor women, less awareness about capacities, low capability to bear risks, problems of work with male workers, neglect by financial institutions, be short of of self-confidence, lack of professional education, mobility constraints and few of interaction with successful entrepreneurs are major problems of women entrepreneurship development in India. Therefore, there is need of incessant attempt to encourage, inspire, motivate and co-operate with women entrepreneurs, awareness programmes should be conducted on a mass level with the purpose of creating awareness among women about the various areas to carry out business.

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